

Preparation, Synthesis and Mass Spectral Studies of 3-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-thiazolo-[2,3,*c*][1,2,4]-triazepine Derivatives

B. V. ALAKA*, D. PATNAIK and M. K. ROUT**

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3

Manuscript received 17 August 1981, revised 14 June 1982, accepted 12 August 1982

Preparation of 3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-thiazolo[2,3-*c*][1,2,4]-triazepine derivatives (I, II and III) through the condensation of 2-hydrazino-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-thiazole with ω -benzoyl acetophenone, acetylacetone and ethylacetoacetate and their mass spectral analysis is reported.

THE importance and extensive use of seven membered heterocyclic compounds like Serax and Megadon¹ as psychosedative and tranquilising agents prompted us to prepare similar seven membered ring system fused to thiazole nucleus and we have prepared the following three compounds, I, II and III.

Condensation of 2-hydrazino-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-thiazole², prepared from 2-chloro-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-thiazole, with ω -benzoyl acetophenone, acetyl acetone and ethylacetoacetate gave I, II and III, respectively. The intermediates (IV) were also isolated from the reactions. All attempts for cyclisation of the intermediate failed, even after prolonged heating with glacial acetic acid.

IR spectrum of IVb showed absorption at 1725 cm⁻¹ (CO₂Et) while that of III showed a band at 1640 cm⁻¹ (>C=O). IR spectrum of IVa showed

absorption at 1640 cm⁻¹ (-C(=O)-C₆H₅) while that of I and II showed the absence of this band. The mass spectra of I-III confirmed their structure.

* Author for correspondence.

** Present address: Vice Chancellor, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar.

Chart 1

Chart 2

TABLE I

Compound	Crystallising solvent	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	S
I	Chloroform-Pet. ether	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	240	50	67.89 (67.92)	3.76 (3.77)	13.01 (13.20)	7.53 (7.54)
II	Pet. ether	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	196-200	70	55.98 (56.0)	4.34 (4.33)	18.65 (18.66)	10.60 (10.66)
III	Ethanol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	220-21	60	51.60 (51.65)	3.29 (3.31)	18.50 (18.54)	10.56 (10.50)
IVa	Ethanol	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	228-30	40	65.05 (65.15)	4.01 (4.07)	10.36 (10.40)	7.20 (7.23)
IVb	Ethanol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	235-37	40	51.70 (51.72)	4.32 (4.31)	16.0 (16.09)	9.89 (9.91)

The melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds were routinely checked by tlc. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were determined on a Varian Mat CH-7 instrument at 70 e. v. using direct inlet.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3-(p-nitrophenyl)-thiazole-[2,3-c][1,2,4]-triazepine derivatives (I-III): A mixture of 2-hydrazino-4-(p-nitrophenyl)-thiazole (2.36 g; 0.01 mole), ω-benzoylacetophenone/acetylacetone/ethylacetoacetate (0.01 mole) and glacial acetic acid (10-35 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. The solid obtained on cooling was filtered, washed and dried. The intermediate products (IV) were isolated by fractional crystallisation of this solid with suitable solvents. All the compounds (I-IV) were purified by repeated crystallisation (Table 1).

References

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